

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of study

Energy has been defined as the ability to do work. This definition encompasses energy in its various forms as it is measured in terms of work done; be it lifting of a load with a crane, riding a bicycle, drying wet clothes or cooking a meal. All these will require different forms of energy.. The word ‘solar’ literary means connected with the sun. Hence solar energy is energy from the sun which can be in form of light for illuminating the earth and for photosynthesis or in form of heat (radiation) for heating up the earth, drying clothes and for preservation of some food crops.(Okafor *et al.*, 2016)

Every minute the sun radiates about 5.68×10^{26} calories of energy and the earth intercepts only 2.55×10^{18} calories (NRF, 2010). This represents only 2000 millionth of the total solar energy sent into the space. The total solar energy is estimated to be 30,000 times greater than the total annual energy of the world (Mgbemu, 2005). The term ‘power’ is not to be interchanged with ‘energy’. Just as energy is the ability to do work, power is the rate at which work is done. Hence, power can be said to be how much energy is being utilized per unit time. Thus power is what puts energy into use. Hence power can be said to be how much energy is being Thus, power is what puts energy into use. In general, when power is mentioned, the famous formula; Power (P) = Current (I) x Voltage (V) comes to mind. This is because power is taken to mean the form of energy which makes it readily available to use; hence the electrical energy. Thus, electrical energy readily puts all other forms of energy into consideration in terms of their quick conversion and usage. Electrical energy is therefore a hub for other forms of energy since it is easily stored and readily available. Solar power therefore simply means solar energy for electricity or the sun for electricity

according to Alexander, (1989). It (solar power = solar energy being converted to electrical energy) therefore puts the vast energy of the sun into use.

Technology had continued to advance and better techniques of grass cutting has been invented and constantly improved upon. This gave birth to the invention of lawn mower. According to Merriam-Webster Dictionary, a lawn mower is a machine used for cutting grass or lawns. A lawn is any area of grass; mostly tough grass which is neatly cut like in a private garden or a public park.

A lawn mower is a machine that is used to cut grass in a lawn. The blades of the lawn mower are generally powered by pushing the mower forward. Lawn mowers are classified based on different criteria. Dutta *et al.*, (2016) classified lawn mower according to the axis of rotation of blades we may have reel lawn mowers (in which the axis is horizontal) and rotary lawn mowers (in which the axis is vertical). Solar powered lawn mower can be described as the application of solar energy to power an electric motor which in turn rotates a blade which does the mowing of a lawn. Different designs have been made; each to suit a particular need or convenience.

1.2 Statement of problem

Over the years, there have been numerous developments in lawn mower technology. But with technological advancement, there also arises the need to check the impact of machines on the environment as well as on man. This project work through the design and fabrication of solar powered lawn mower solves the following problem:

- I. Pollution: Gasoline or diesel powered lawn mower tends to release wasted carbon content in the atmosphere thereby adding to the ever increasing carbon pool of the atmosphere which is unsafe to mankind. The excess carbon leads to Global warming which results into high level of temperature across the earth surface. Solar powered lawn mower makes use of solar energy which is a cleaner, greener and safer for the environment.
- II. Human Effort: Energy expended to start other conventional mowers is conserved when using solar powered mower. The latter also eliminates downtime by frequent trips to the gas station for fill-ups and danger associated with gasoline spillage.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

- I. The major objective of this study is to design, develop and fabricate a solar powered lawn mower.

The specific objectives are:

- I. To design solar powered lawn mower using computer aided software; Autodesk Inventor.

- II. To fabricate the designed lawn mower using necessary materials and fabrication technique.

1.4 Scope and Limitation

The designed and fabricated solar powered lawn mower is designed to be used light jobs and in lawn free of stones.

1.5 Significance of Research

The fabricated solar powered lawn mower will help harness the sun's enormous energy. Since it is not ran on fossil fuel, it solves the problem of environmental and noise pollution. It does not emit greenhouse gases thereby not adding to the adverse effect of global warming.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 History of lawn mower technology

The first lawn mower was invented in 1830 by Edwin Beard Budding (www.oldlawnmowerclub.co.uk). He was said to obtain the idea after watching a machine in a local cloth mill which used a cutting cylinder mounted on a bench to trim clothes for a smooth finish after weaving. Budding realized that a similar concept could be used to cut grass if the mechanism is mounted in a wheel frame to enable the blades rotate close to the lawn surface. These early machines were made of cast iron and featured a large rear roller with a cutting cylinder (reel) in the front. Cast iron gear wheel transmitted power from the rear roller to the cutting cylinder. In 1832, Ransoms of Ipswich (under license) began the making of Budding's mower. This company is today the world's largest manufacturer of lawn care equipment. By mid-1850, Thomas Green developed a mower which used chains to transmit power from the rear roller to the cutting cylinder (www.oldlawnmowerclub.co.uk). It was called 'Silens Messor' meaning silentcutter. The machines were found comparatively lighter and quieter than the gear driven machines that preceded them(www.en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lawn-mower). By late 1890, motorized mowers appeared as light weight petrol engines and small steam power units became available. In US, gasoline powered lawn mowers were first manufactured in 1914 by Ideal Power Mower Company of Lansing, Michigan, based on patent by Ransom E.Olds. Ideal Power Mower also introduced the world's first self-propelled riding

lawn tractor in 1922 known as the “Triplex” (www.reoldmuseum.org). Electric powered mowers and rotary cutting machines emerged in the 1920’s and 1930’s.

2.2 Solar powered lawn mower models

Dipin and Chandrasekhar (2014) studied solar powered vision based Robotic Lawn Mower. It showed the design of a microcontroller and sensor based robotic lawn mower mechanism. This robotic mowing device was solar powered and its battery gets charged from sunlight while mowing on the lawn or even manually. Ultrasonic sensors were used for avoiding obstacles and humidity sensor for checking humidity level in the lawn. Passive infrared sensor (PIR) was used to detect human interaction near the device in operation. Android smart phone was used for capturing images of the lawn as per requirement. This design is targeted as an alternate green option against the popular but environmentally hazardous gas powered lawn mower. The design is built on a mobile robot which communicates with a computer through a zigbee module. A GUI (Graphical User Interface) has been created in MATLAB for the selection of cutting design/pattern of the lawn by the operator.

Tanimola *et al.*,(2014) studied on design and development of a solar powered lawn mower. They tried to achieve a solar powered lawn mower model that used solar energy with the help of a solar panel and solar photovoltaic cells to run an electric motor. The electric motor was coupled to the cutting blades. The photons from sun hit the photovoltaic cell and as a result, flow of electrons start leading to direct current. A 1.5 HP (Horse Power) motor is used and a 12 volt battery supply electric power to run the motor. They performed detailed analysis to estimate the torque produced in the blade and whether it is sufficient

to perform the intended job. Also stress analysis was performed for the frame and the handle of the lawn mower. After design and development of the lawn mower, it was tested on four different species of grass.

Satwik *et al.*,(2015) performed design and fabrication of lever operated solar lawn mower and contact stress analysis of spur gears. They tried to develop a height adjustable mechanism for the cutting blade. The mechanism involves a pair of spur gears of different face width and a lever which adjusts the rotor height such that the smaller spur gear slides on the face width of the larger spur gear. An arduino board was used to control the speed of the rotor blade and obstacle detection. Solar panel receives sunlight and powers the battery which in turn runs the motor. Battery and motor selection were done after design analysis of blade. Active stresses on the spur gears are calculated by using AGMA and Hertz equation and also Finite Element Analysis.(Figure 1 and Figure 2)

Figure 1: CAD Model of lawn mower. (Dutta *et al*, 2016)

Figure 2: Gears mounted of different face width. (Dutta *et al*, 2016)

Okafor *et al.* (2016) also studied the development of solar powered lawn mower. The lawn mower had a field capacity of 0.13m²/s. It was made of a twin solar panel of 75A/130W capacity each which charges the battery of the mower. The lawn mower had a cutting blade attached to a 2.1KW, 24V DC electric motor, driven by two 12Volts 75AH lead accumulator connected in series. They observed that it took approximately two days; 48 hours for the lawn mower to be fully charged. They also observed at full charge, it could be used in mowing a total area of 552 square metres of lawn.

2.3 Gas powered lawn mower models

Gabele,(1997) reported on exhaust emissions from four stroke lawn mower internal combustion engines. The studies characterized exhaust emissions from new and in use four stroke lawn mower engines. The impact of reformulated fuel on emission rates and composition was examined by testing two fuels: (1) A 1990 baseline gasoline and (2) A California Reformulated Gasoline (CaRFG) Program. The various instruments used for the test experiments were emission analyzers, engine dynamometer controller and constant volume sample that were used to collect the data during the exhaust emissions test. The data were entered into the computer in real time. Exhaust gas emissions were generated by operating the engines over the composite six mode test cycle. The exhaust emissions test were conducted on 10 engines which had different values of displacement, age and time in use, rated power, maximum test torque and different types of valves. It was found that as compared to the to the baseline gasoline, the reformulated was an oxygenated fuel that has lower olefin and aromatic levels, lower T 90 (temperature at which 90% of the fuel boils-off), and lower Reid vapor pressure. The (California Reformulated Gasoline) CaRFG Program gasoline also had a lower sulfur content that enabled catalysts to operate at higher conversion efficiencies in reducing pollutant emissions. The author concluded that lower NMOG (non

methane organic gas), CO(Carbon monoxide) , RWE (reactivity weighted emissions) and aggregate toxic emission rates were observed with the newer mowers and with the reformulated gasoline. Conversely higher NO_x emission rates were observed with these same engines and fuel.

2.4 Autonomous lawn mower models

Newstadt *et al.*,(2000) studied on a Global Positioning System (GPS) aided autonomous lawnmower. They tried to develop an efficient hybrid lawn mower. It consisted of a modified DGPS (Differential global positioning receiver system), a modified chassis, new wheel encoders, a more advanced control system, digital compass and a safety system. Furthermore acoustic sensors and a laser ranging systems had been added in order to supply obstacle detection capabilities. The DGPS(Differential global positioning receiver system) system based on carrier phase measurements provided accuracy at the centimeter level. This lawnmower was lightweight, yet robust for operation. It was framed with angle iron. The mounting surfaces were shielded with high strength steel sheeting with plywood covering the steel. Furthermore, a shelving system was incorporated to offer the maximum flexibility to the layout and construction. A new shaft coupling mechanism was fabricated to link the gas engine to the alternator shaft and the engine. It consisted of control software to control the path planning through the remote base station for testing and monitoring purposes. The digital compass was used to compute the azimuth angle of a lawn mower. Furthermore, a reliable safety system was implemented on-board with a remote controlled emergency stop.

Patil *et al.*(2003) studied on design and implementation of automatic lawn cutter. They developed a cordless automatic lawn mower so that the user could specify the area to be mowed and also the height of the grass as per their requirement by using the keypad. The design contains a microcontroller like *Atmega 16*, multiple sensors, Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) and keyboard. The microcontroller *Atmega 16* was used for analog to digital conversions from the sensors. It also controls the speed of the wheels. The battery can be charged by using power supply and solar panel. A sensor ADXL335 is used which is an accelerometer to detect orientation based on pre calibrated axis orientation. Further a high performance sonar module is used to detect an object in its vision from 20 feet away and for inserting input a keyboard is used. Three DC motors are used. One DC (Direct Current) motor is connected to the linear blade and others are connected to the (Direct Current).

Ray., (2001) studied on tele-autonomous heavy duty robotic lawn mower. It concerned with development of a heavy duty lawn mowing machine that was richly instrumented with sensors and computational support. This provided a hybrid capability between pure tele-operation and full automation. In this model the author used a tri-level control strategy where the three levels of control were reactive (low level), anticipatory (middle level) and planning (top level). The two lower levels (reactive and anticipatory) basically provide local support for obstacle collision avoidance at both an imminent and local level, with the top level planning being provided by the operator. The instruments used in the model were Erwin Sick scanning laser range finder (up to 50 meters range), Phase mode/ Differential Global Positioning System Optical Gyroscope (with vertical axis), Stereo Video Camera Pair, Web Camera (with its own IP address),

Long Range Laser Rangefinder (up to 400 meters), Denning Bar Code Reading Localizer (up to 30 meters) etc.

Chandler *et al.* (2000) reported on the next generation autonomous lawn mower. The developed autonomous lawnmower robot was capable of learning its environment through training. Once learned, the robot would be capable of navigating through its environment that avoided obstacles by means of its sensors. The mower could operate using machine learning techniques. This allows the mower to recognize objects in the mowing area like flower beds, sidewalks, trees, driveways, etc., using computer vision. The use of vision will allow the mower to determine whether it is cut or uncut grass and act accordingly in a pattern. The mower would need training by a human operator in order to learn what objects to avoid and where and how to mow. If the mower realizes where a bare patch of yard is, it can release fertilizer to promote the growth of grass, or release ant killer if it comes across an ant hill. This makes the mower a "lawn maintainer" instead of just a lawnmower. Sensors for obstacle avoidance and range detection were computer vision system, infrared sensors and sonar. A local positioning system (LPS) allowed the mower to know where it was in the yard. All these sensors combined so that the mower can make informed decisions about its environment. The mower would also need to charge its batteries. This is done with the help of a charging station placed somewhere in the mowing area.

Singh and Singh,(2015) performed design and analysis of wireless remote controlled lawn mower. They tried to make a smaller, lighter, efficient, environment friendly and direct current powered lawn mower for better handling and endurance. An adjustable cutting height motor was introduced for better mowing of grass at intricate locations (Figure 3). An innovative design was made and stress and deflection analysis was

performed by using ANSYS (Figure 4, Figure 5). The stresses developed and deflection of various elements of mower has been shown in the form of colour coding.

Figure 3: CAD Model (Dutta *et al*, 2016)

Figure 4: Von Mises Stress. (Dutta *et al*, 2016)

Figure 5: Deflection of base. (Dutta *et al*, 2016)

Sujendran and Vanitha, (2014) reported on smart lawn mower for grass trimming operation. They presented a model of an automated lawn mower that consists of linear blades operated with the help of a motor. The power supply of the motor was a battery that could be charged either by electricity or by solar panel. An infra-red sensor was provided for obstacle

detection that prevents possible hardware damage. A path planning algorithm was proposed by the authors in whom they tried to achieve three modes-minimum time mode, minimum energy mode and mixed mode. However, this was a compromise between the other two modes. As shown in the circuit diagram in figure (6), the battery runs the motor this in turn actuates the blades. The solar panel recharges the battery. The height of cutting is adjusted by means of a link mechanism via a lift rod. A simple flow chart provided by the authors for the movement of the lawn mower is given in (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Circuit diagram of the model. (Dutta *et al*, 2016)

Figure 7: Flow Chart of the model. (Dutta *et al*, 2016)

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1 Feasibility

The materials and equipment used for this work were gotten locally.

3.2 Design methodology

3.2.1 Selection of mowing blade and actuator for the mowing blade.

According to Atkins (1984), the shear force required to cut a grass by a sharp object is less than 10 Newtons, depending on the height of the grass, type of the grass as well as grass density in the area. The blade is made of stainless steel to promote efficiency and also to resist natural chemical phenomenon such as rusting.

The following calculations will be needed to calculate the power needed to be generated by the blade to cut the grass.

$$\text{Area of the blade} = (\text{Length} \times \text{breadth}) \text{ of blade.} = 200\text{mm} \times 30\text{mm} = 6000\text{mm}^2 \text{-----(1)}$$

$$\text{Volume of the blade} = \text{Area of blade} \times \text{Thickness} = 6000\text{mm}^2 \times 0.3 = 1800\text{mm}^3 \text{-----(2)}$$

$$\text{Density of steel(Sign, 2005)} = 7922\text{kg/m}^3$$

$$\text{Thus, Mass of blade} = 7922 \times \text{Volume of blade} = 7922 \times 1800 \times 10^{-9} = 0.014\text{kg} \text{-----(3)}$$

$$\text{Force} = \text{Mass of blade} \times \text{acceleration due to gravity (9.81)m/s}^2 = 0.014\text{kg} \times 9.81 = 0.14\text{N} \text{-(4)}$$

$$\text{Therefore, torque (T) required to turn a blade} = \text{Force} \times \text{radius of blade}; \text{ where radius of blade} = 200/2 = 100\text{mm. Torque} = 0.14 \times 100 = 14\text{Nmm} = 0.014\text{Nm} \text{-----(5)}$$

Angular Velocity and Force produced by blade

$w = 2\pi N / 60$ Where $N = \text{number of turns of motor in revolutions per minute} = 1450 \text{rpm}$

$$w = 2 \times 3.142 \times 1450 / 60 = 151.86 \text{rad/s} \text{-----(6)}$$

$$\text{Power} = Tw = 0.014 \times 151.86 = 2.13 \text{W} \text{----- (7)}$$

Converting the determined power to horsepower = 0.003hp.

For our design, a motor of 0.5hp was chosen.

$$\text{Thus the Centrifugal force by the blade; } F_c = mw^2r = 0.014 \times 151.86^2 \times 0.100 = 32.29 \text{N} \text{---(8)}$$

Tanimola, *et al*, (2014) noted that the higher the power generated by the blade, the greater the efficiency of the lawn mower. Hence considering the power required to move the blade is important for greater efficiency.

3.2.2 Battery size

Batteries are available in various volts and ampere hour range. To determine the one to use, consideration was given to the voltage and the ampere hour rating. Since the motor is 0.5hp, then a 12V battery was selected. The ampere hour measures the length of time the battery will discharge while in use and is not charging. A 17 ampere hour battery will give a 17 amp of current for one hour and the current required by the motor is less than that.

3.2.3 Charging Station

The average sunshine in Uyo, Nigeria located at latitude ($5^{\circ}18'53.7''\text{N}$) from January to December covering a period of seven years is (Mfon et al, 2013);

$$(3.10 + 3.61 + 2.92 + 3.15 + 3.40 + 2.56 + 1.47 + 1.24 + 1.99 + 2.75 + 3.35 + 2.84) / 12 = 2.70 \text{ hours}$$

The solar panel that was used for the construction is rated Capacity of Solar panel used for the construction of the solar powered lawnmower is rated 30 Watts, 18 volts consisting of 24 cells. Hence according to Khurmi and Gupta (2000);

$$\text{Power} = IV \text{-----(9)}$$

Where I = current; V- voltage

$$I = P/V$$

$$I = 30/18 = 1.67 \text{V}$$

The solar panel is connected to the battery via a solar charging controller and from the battery to the motor. Also, an electric switch is connected to the circuit to control flow of current.

3.2.4 Design for Frame

Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) pipes were used in the construction of the frame. PVC pipes are strong, lightweight, flexible, easy to handle and economical, it is also resistant to corrosion. The frame provides support for the electric motor, battery as well as handle frame. The deck transmit a load of 15kg to the wheel equally and length of each is 300mm.

The bending moment $M = PL/4$ -----(10)

Where P is the load= $15 \times 10 = 150\text{N}$

But the load is equally shared, hence for each it will be $150/4 = 37.5\text{N}$

$M = PL/4 = (37.5 \times 300)/4 = 2.81\text{KNmm}$

Yield stress = 55N/mm^2

Allowable shear stress = Ultimate stress/yield stress = $0.53 \times 55\text{N/mm}^2 = 29.15\text{N/mm}^2$ – (11)

The sectional modulus(z) according to Khurmi and Gupta (2000).

Sectional modulus(z) = bending moment/shear stress.-----(12)

$= 2.81 \times 10^3 / 29.15 = 96.40\text{mm}^3$

3.3 Computer Aided Drawings and Design(CADD)

Figure 8: CAD design showing top view of the project.

Figure 9: CAD showing the exploded view of the project

Figure 10: CAD showing the exploded section of solar panel, joints and blade

Figure 11: CAD showing the side view of arm and deck.

3.4 Experimental Test Procedure

The solar powered lawnmower was tested on four different species of elephant grass, stubborn grass; spare grass and carpet grass of 4500mm by 4500mm field noting the time spent cutting the field. Ten replicates of the test were carried out and the Performance Efficiency of the machine was then determined. The field capacity was also determined by using:

$$C = WSE/10 \text{-----(13)}$$

Where,

W=Width of cut (km)

S=Speed (km/hr). From equation (vi), Converting 151.86rad/s to Km/h ; $v(\text{km/h}) = 3.6 \times r \times w(\text{rad/s})$; $3.6 \times 0.1 \times 151.86 = 54.66 \text{km/h}$ -----**(14)**

E = Efficiency. (%)

$$C = 4.5 \times 10^{-3} \times 54.66 \times 0.09 / 10 = 2.21 \times 10^{-1} \text{ha/hr}$$

CHAPTER FOUR
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plate 1: Picture showing the prototype of the skeletal framework and the solar panel.

Plate 2: Picture showing the blade, DC motor and lithium cells

Plate 3: Picture showing the lithium battery packed with the charge controller and voltmeter.

The Solar powered lawn mower was designed and developed. Test were carried out using four species of grasses in the University of Uyo and the result obtained is summarized as presented in Table 4.1

Table 1: Table showing the Average height of grass before and after mowing of each sample plot.

Sample plot	Average height of the grass before mowing (mm)	Average height of the grass after mowing (mm)	Expected height of the grass after mowing
Elephant grass	214	80	90
Stubborn grass	204	82	90
Spear grass	100	62	70
Carpet grass	60.5	46.5	40

Table 2: Chi square Statistical Table $x^2 = (O-E)^2/E$

Average height of the grass after mowing (O)(mm)	Expected height of the grass after mowing (E) (mm)	O-E	(O-E) ²	$x^2 = (O-E)^2/E$	Time(s)
80	90	-10	100	1.1	490
82	90	-8	64	0.71	470
62	70	-8	64	0.91	450
46.5	40	6.5	42.25	1.05	430

From Table 1, the average height of the grasses after mowing was lesser than the expected after the machine have been adjusted to a height for the four species of grasses. Less time was spent in cutting the grasses. The efficiency of the machine was found to be 90% and the effective field capacity was 2.21×10^{-1} ha/hr. The confidence level was calculated and Chi-square statistical analytical method was used to analyze the result at alpha level of 5%. The result shows that there is no significant difference between the effects of the machine on different types of lawns as shown on Table 2.

From Table 1, it can be deduced that the reduction in the height of cut grass occurred in the case of stubborn grass. The initial height being 204mm and the final height being 82mm giving a difference of 122mm. For elephant grass, the initial height being 214mm and the final height being 80mm, a difference of 134mm. for the spear grass, the initial height was 100mm and the final height was 62mm, a difference of 38mm. For the carpet grass, the initial height was 60.5mm and the final height was 46.5mm giving a difference of 14mm.

From these figures, it shows that the machine performed best on stubborn grass followed by the elephant grass. The machine was able to reduce the height of the carpet to 46.5mm due to the very soft nature of this type of grass. In all, the machine has performed creditably well.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion:

The Solar powered lawn mower was designed, fabricated, coupled and tested for efficiency

Contribution to knowledge:

The fabricated solar powered lawnmower will meet the challenges of environmental protection and low cost of operation since there is no cost for fueling, the noise emanating from the machine is at a reduced level. The solar powered lawn mower has been developed for the use of residences and establishments that have lawns where tractor driven mowers could not be used. The machine's capacity is adequate for its purpose. The machine has proved to be a possible replacement for the gasoline powered lawn mowers.

Recommendation:

There is need for advancement and improved studies on this project work. Other area of interest includes the use of sensors in solar powered lawn mower, development of a hybrid type mower (Solar powered DC and AC charging unit). There is also need for mass production of the designed solar powered lawn mower so that it could be of market value and compete against other conventional lawn mowers.

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